

The high-yielding varieties developed at IRRI have so far failed to perform satisfactorily in northern Iran, probably because of the low temperatures. However, some selections of IR498 and IR533 have yielded from 5 to 6 t/ha. IR5 also performed comparatively better in southern Iran, and efforts are being made to introduce it into that area. Century Patna, an improved variety from the USA, was found to yield higher than local varieties in farmers' fields. It is tall but stiff-stemmed and yields about 5 t/ha. It has long and fine grains but its cooking quality is poor. Because it yields more and is attractive in the field, farmers in Mazandaran province grow it under the name Misbah. Its area is spreading from year to year. It now occupies about 40,000 ha in that province.

Amol #1 is a semidwarf high-yielding variety developed from a 1965 cross of Tarom Firooz Kande/TN1. Tarom Firooz Kande is a local, tall, low-yielding variety with good eating quality. It was released for cultivation in Mazandaran province in 1973. It has long, slender kernels with acceptable cooking quality and matures about 140 days after sowing. It is more suitable in warmer areas. Sterility is a problem under low temperature in Gilan province. A number of other short-statured advanced lines that are capable of yielding from 5 to 6 t/ha and possess acceptable cooking quality are being tested in yield trials.

A new source of resistance to several diseases and pests of rice

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Rice breeders are always looking for new sources of resistance to different diseases and insects so that they can incorporate polygenic resistance into new varieties. R-68-1 is a tall variety that was bred at the Central Rice Research Station,

Raipur, M.P., of Jawaharlal Nehru Agricultural University, by crossing Rikku, a Japanese variety, with R4 (Surmatia), a local indica variety. R-68-1 has shown resistant to moderately resistant reaction to bacterial blight and bacterial leaf streak under artificial inoculation tests at Raipur, and to leaf smut, false smut, *Sogatata*, gall fly, and

green leafhopper in field screening trials. It has been extensively used in the crossing program of this station. Several of its derivatives have shown resistant to moderately resistant reactions against different diseases and pests in testing by the National Breeding Nursery and the National Screening Nursery at different sites in India, including Raipur.

Some derivatives of crosses that involve R-68-1 as a parent and that show resistant reaction to different diseases and insects. Central Rice Research Station, Jawaharlal Nehru Agricultural University, Raipur, M. P., India.

Cross combination	Derivative	Diseases and insects ^a
R-68-1/CR-10-4050	R 2329	BB
	R 2330	BB, WH
	R 2331	BB, FS, WH
	R 2335	BB, FS
	R 2338	LS
	R 2341	BB
	R 2343	BB, FS
	R 2386	BB, RTV, Sh. B, WH
	R 2389	BB, BLS, FS, GLH
	783	St.B
	R6-2390	BB
	R6-2520	FS
	R6-2521	BPH
	R6-2522	BPH, FS
R-68-1/TN1	R 2356	RTV, WH
	R 2357	WH
	R 2358	BB, BLS, FS
	R 2359	WH
	R 2363	BB
	R 2364	WH
R-68-1/Jaya	R 2325	BB
	R 2380	BB
	R 2381	BB, BLS, LS
	R 2384	GM, RTV
	R4-2517	BB, Blast, FS
	R4-2518	BB, Blast, FS
	R4-2519	BB, Blast, LS, FS
	R4-2528	BB, FS
	R4-2529	BB, FS, LS
	DGWG/R-68-1	R30-2549

^aBB = bacterial blight; BLS = bacterial leaf streak; LS = leaf smut; FS = false smut; RTV = rice tungro virus; Sh.B. = sheath blight; WH = white head; St.B = stem borer; GM = gall midge.